

IEA Task 52 Working Group on TI

Overview, objectives and plan

22.09.2025 – IEA Task 52 General Meeting in Kassel

Richard Fruehmann

Working group overview

- 48 Participants
 - 12 different countries
 - 38 – Industry, 9 – Academia, 1 - Government
- Activities since Berlin (May 2024)
 - 5 online meetings
 - 1 sub-group meeting (literature review)
 - 3 Lunchtime webinars
 - The lidar probe volume averaging effect on the turbulence intensity measured by continuous-wave lidar
 - Motion compensation for turbulence intensity measurement from floating lidars
 - Wind turbulence model based on 30-second periods

Objectives

- How can TI measurements obtained with lidars be either adapted or interpreted to facilitate the use of these measurements in different applications for the wind energy industry?
 - energy yield assessment
 - power performance measurement
 - load calculations
 - lifetime extension
- Adoption of the technology will require industry accepted standards. How can we pave the road towards such a standard?
 - a harmonised approach to deal with all TI questions?
 - a separate approach for each application?
 - a separate approach for each lidar type (e.g.: vertical profiler, nacelle mounted, scanner)?

Objectives

Goals 2023:

- Update on Expert Report (towards end of task)
- Collection of current activities on Lidar TI (towards end of year)
- Publicly accessible database of nacelle lidar data (timeline unclear)

- How can TI measurements obtained with lidars be either adapted or interpreted to facilitate the use of these measurements in different applications for the wind energy industry?
 - energy yield assessment
 - power performance measurement
 - load calculations
 - lifetime extension
- Adoption of the technology will require industry accepted standards. How can we pave the road towards such a standard?
 - a harmonised approach to deal with all TI questions?
 - a separate approach for each application?
 - a separate approach for each lidar type (e.g.: vertical profiler, nacelle mounted, scanner)?
- Propose a structure around which a future standard for Lidar TI can be developed.

Plan & Deliverables

- Literature review
 - Applications
 - Technology
 - Industry practices
 - Barriers to adoption/acceptance
 - Strategy for developing useful standards
 - Where in the current IEC 61400-12 & -50 (and others) does TI feature
 - What can be formulated in a generic sense and what is application/technology specific?
- *Update to the Expert report from Task 32?*
- *Technical Note / White Paper?*

Workshop aims

- Structure the literature review
- Structure the final deliverable

Plan & Deliverables

- Regular Meetings
 - Monthly meetings to discuss progress and present contributions from the community
- Literature review:
 - Collate literature suggestions
 - Formulate a draft summary of the report
 - Publish the summary report
- TI-strategy:
 - Document where TI is relevant in the IEC standards
 - Collate ideas on how to structure the process of including lidar TI in the IEC standard
 - Formulate draft recommendation
 - Publish recommendation

		collate literature	formulate draft	publish report	document TI in the IEC	draft a chapter on recommendations
2024	June					
	July					
	August					
	September					
	October					
	November					
2025	December					
	January					
	February					
	March					
	April					
	May					
	June					
	July					
	August					
	September					
	October					
	November					
December						
2026	January					
	February					
	March					
	April					
	May					

Thank you

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